

SOLITARY BONE CYST AND TREATMENT

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1. Abstract

Etiopathogenesis of solitary bone cyst is unclear. Solitary bone cyst are benign tumor-like lesions which most frequently metaphyseal-diaphyseal region of the humerus and femur of children and adolescents. The classical treatment method used was curettage and grafting. However, there is a high recurrence risk after surgery. In this paper 14 cases diagnosed in Cerrahpasa Medical Faculty between 1976-1988 have been evaluated.

Keywords: *Solitary Bone Cyst, Simple Bone Cyst Bone Cyst*

2. Introduction

Solitary bone cyst was first described by German pathologist R. Virchow in 1876 (1). Solitary bone cyst makes 3% of all benign bone lesions (2). Solitary bone cysts are usually located at the metaphysis of long bones or near growth plates. Frequently seen in humerus femur and calcaneus. Cause of the origin is not known. Pathology in endochondral bone formation after trauma (3), high pressure building within bone due to venous occlusion (4) synovial structure entrapment due to postpartum trauma (5) are the present theories of origin (5). Clinically most of the patients may be asymptomatic some might have pain due to microfractures also pathological fractures may appear. According to Norman there is a risk of 53% pathologic fractures (6). The location of pathological fractures was stated as 38.6 at humerus 35.1 % at femur 13% in tibia in series reported, Spencer, Norman and Garceau (6,7).

Standard radiology, CT scans MRI and bone scintigraphy is useful for diagnosis. Staging is done according to whether the lesion is active or passive. Active lesions are the lesions seen before the age of ten, near the epiphyseal plate, presenting with balloon-like expansion with thin cortex and showing progressive improvement on follow up (8).

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Figure– 1:

A – Pathological Fracture Due to Solitary Bone Cyst In The Right Humerus

B – Early Postoperative Period

C – 20 Months After Surgery

Male to female ratio is 3/1. Most cases are diagnosed clinically and radiologically. Lymphoma, Ewing sarcoma, Eosinophilic granuloma, enchondroma, fibrous dysplasia, giant cell tumor, aneurysm bone cyst, Brodie abscess, syphilis of bone, tuberculosis, echinococcus cysts, osteolytic osteogenic sarcomas, metastatic bone tumors should be considered in differential diagnosis.

Figure – 2 :

Functions 20 Months After Surgery

There is no established treatment protocol. Injection of chemicals like paraffin, ivory into the cyst, curettage followed by griffonage, filling of cyst with sterile gibbs pellets or dried frozen bone grafts, radical resection, multip forage, intracystic corticosteroid injection are the methods of treatment.

3. Material and Method

Fourteen patients that had adequate follow-up of nineteen cases that were diagnosed with solitary bone cyst between 1976-1988 in orthopedics and traumatology department of Cerrahpasa medical Faculty were included in the study. Six of the patients were female (43%) eight were male (57%). The youngest patient was 8 years old, the oldest was 25 years old with a median of 13.9 years. 71 % of the cases were seen in the second decade. Six of the lesion were in humerus five were in tibia 1in distal fibula 1 in distal tibia and one in iliac bone.

Figure– 3: Solitary Bone Cyst And Pathological Fracture In The Right Humeral Metaphysis

Six of the lesions 43% caused pathological fractures, local pain was present 8 cases 57% palpable expansion was seen in two patients 14.2% 1 case 7.1% was diagnosed with an x ray taken for some other reason. Laboratory studies were normal. Figure 5 figure 6 (Treatment was curettage and iliac bone grafting in six cases 43%, curettage and capitonnage in one case &.1%, local resection and fibular graft in one case (figure1)(figure 2), curettage and bone graft in five cases 35% Figure 3 figure 4 .

- One case treated by multip-forage and leaving a k-wire in the lesion.
- Ten of the cases 72% were passive and four were 28% were active.

Figure – 4:

A – Immediately After Surgery

B – Appearance 10 Months After Surgery

4. Findings

There were three recurrences one was in humerus, and one was in proximal femur curettage and grafting was repeated one case was distal fibula and was treated with multiple forage and k wire insertion to the lesion.

Follow up was minimum 7 months maximum 128 months with a median of 36.4 months.

5. Discussion

First treatment option of solitary bone cyst is curettage of the cyst followed by autografting or allografting. This invasive method's disadvantages of morbidity scar formation and prohibitive cost led researchers to seek for new methods. Sgaglietti et al popularized methylprednisolone acetate injection in 1979 (10). Some authors advocate radical resection due to high recurrence rates (11).

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Figure – 5:

A – Before Surgery

B – Radiographs Immediately After Surgery

In their study Oppenheim and Galleno stated that steroid injection in children older than 5 years of age had only 5% recurrence (12).

In this study we concluded that local steroid injection MPA should be considered a suitable alternative in selected cases being simple, reliable and cost effective because of the high recurrence rate of classical curettage and graft treatment (13).

Figure– 6: X-Ray 13 Months After Surgery

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